

Kinetics and mechanism of binding of Δ and Λ coordination compounds with double helical DNA

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A general method to prepare enantiomerically pure polypyridyl ruthenium(II) complexes is presented, and binding behavior of a series of enantiomerically pure polypyridyl ruthenium(II) complexes to calf thymus DNA has been investigated by circular dichroism, electronic absorption and fluorescence spectroscopies, as well as viscosity and equilibrium dialysis binding studies. Specially, binding of the Δ - and Λ -[Ru(bpy)₂(HPIP)]²⁺ (bpy = 2,2'-bipyridine, HPIP = 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)imidazo[4,5-f][1,10]phenanthroline) to the hexanucleotide d(GTCGAC)₂ was investigated by ¹H NMR spectroscopy. The results suggest that both of the Δ - and Λ -[Ru(bpy)₂(HPIP)]²⁺ bind the d(GTCGAC)₂ by intercalation in the major groove, however, the Λ -enantiomer does not intercalate as deeply as the Δ -enantiomer. Different binding rates of individual enantiomers to DNA are observed through dialysis experiment. The Λ -enantiomer binds more rapidly than the Δ -enantiomer and their different penetration into the DNA base pairs upon binding to the double helix are suggested. For the complexes which bind avidly to DNA by intercalation, there is no noticeable enantioselectivity between the Δ - and Λ -enantiomers. Both of their enantiomers can intercalate into DNA base pairs. While for the weakly DNA-binding complexes, the Δ - and Λ -enantiomers may interact with DNA via different binding modes.

Binding of polypyridyl ruthenium(II) complexes with DNA has been the subject of interest in recent years for their potential application to nucleic acid probes¹⁻⁴. Numerous complexes of this type have been intensively investigated, however, less reports have appeared regarding the interaction of individual enantiomer with DNA, partly due to the difficulties of resolving the enantiomers. The binding of the prototype complex of ruthenium(II) polypyridyl [Ru(phen)₃]²⁺ to DNA has been actively studied⁵⁻¹², although its exact DNA binding mode remains an issue of debate. Barton *et al.*⁶ proposed that the binding occurs through a minor groove surface bound interaction and a major groove intercalated form. However, viscosity measurements for DNA in the presence of each enantiomer of [Ru(phen)₃]²⁺ argue that neither affects the structure of DNA as a classical intercalator would be expected to^{9,10}. NMR and CD spectra of these chiral complexes in the presence of oligonucleotide also support that neither of the enantiomers binds by classical intercalation^{11,12}. On the other hand, there is a consensus of intercalative binding of the dipyridophenazine(DPPZ)ruthenium(II) complexes, [Ru(bpy)₂DPPZ]²⁺ and [Ru(phen)₂DPPZ]²⁺, with DNA¹³⁻²⁰, which has been unambiguously confirmed by NMR^{15,16}, resonance Raman^{17,18}, linear dichroism spectra¹⁹, as well as viscosity measurements²⁰. These complexes show no photoluminescence in aqueous solution at ambient temperature but display intense lumi-

nescence upon binding to DNA, displaying the characteristics of molecular light switches. Based on NMR evidence Dupureur and Barton^{15,16} proposed that [Ru(phen)₂DPPZ]²⁺ intercalates from the major groove. Alternatively, Tuite *et al.*²¹ suggested that the metal complex intercalates from the minor groove on the basis of the fact of retention of binding to T4 DNA in which all 5-hydroxymethylcytosine residues are glycosylated in the major groove.

As our ongoing focus on the interactions of polypyridyl ruthenium(II) complexes with DNA²²⁻²⁹, we present herein a general method of preparation of enantiomerically pure polypyridylruthenium(II) complexes, and observe the interactions of these chiral complexes with DNA. The following are the prepared chiral complexes: Δ - and Λ -[Ru(bpy)₂(HPIP)](PF₆)₂, (Δ -1 and Λ -1, bpy = 2,2'-bipyridine, HPIP = 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)imidazo[4,5-f][1,10]phenanthroline), Δ - and Λ -[Ru(bpy)₂(HNAIP)](PF₆)₂, (Δ -2 and Λ -2, HNAIP = 2-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)imidazo[4,5-f][1,10]phenanthroline), Δ - and Λ -[Ru(bpy)₂(HNOIP)](PF₆)₂, (Δ -3 and Λ -3, HNOIP = 2-(2-hydroxy-5-nitrophenyl)imidazo[4,5-f][1,10]phenanthroline), Δ - and Λ -[Ru(bpy)₂(DPPZ)](PF₆)₂ (Δ -4 and Λ -4).

Syntheses and resolving of the enantiomers:

The procedure of preparing the chiral complexes is presented in Scheme 1. Isolation of the enantiomers was

Scheme 1

achieved by using the Δ - and Λ - $[Ru(bpy)_2(py)_2]^{2+}$ as enantiomerically pure chiral building blocks, which have shown high thermal stereochemical stability and have been widely used to prepare stereochemically pure multiruthenium complexes³⁰. The enantiomeric purity of these complexes was assayed by CD spectroscopy. Assignment of the absolute configuration of the enantiomers was made by applying excitation theory³¹ and/or comparing with similar complexes of known configuration³².

Binding of the Δ - and Λ - $[Ru(bpy)_2(HPIP)]^{2+}$ to the hexanucleotide $d(GTCGAC)_2$:

Binding of the enantiomers of $[Ru(bpy)_2(HPIP)]^{2+}$ to the hexanucleotide $d(GTCGAC)_2$ was investigated by ¹H NMR spectroscopy. In the NMR spectrum of $d(GTCGAC)_2$ with added Δ - and Λ - $[Ru(bpy)_2(HPIP)]^{2+}$, only one set of hexanucleotide and metal complex resonances were observed, indicating that neither enantiomers bind with slow exchange kinetics³³ (on the NMR time-scale). Addition of either the Δ - or Λ -enantiomer induced significant broadening of the DNA proton resonances, indicating that both enantiomers bind with intermediate exchange kinetics. Addition of Δ - $[Ru(bpy)_2(HPIP)]^{2+}$ to $d(GTCGAC)_2$ induced significant upfield shifts for the HPIP resonances, with the bpy resonances showing only small shifts. Addition of Λ - $[Ru(bpy)_2(HPIP)]^{2+}$ to the hexanucleotide induced a similar upfield shifts for the HPIP protons, but with somewhat smaller magnitude. The observed chemical shift changes upon binding the hexanucleotide for both HPIP and bpy ligand protons for Δ - and Λ - $[Ru(bpy)_2(HPIP)]^{2+}$ are compiled in Table 1. Larger perturbations were observed for the HPIP ligand protons, while much smaller perturbations were observed for the ancillary bpy ligands. The observed intermediate exchange binding kinetics and the magnitude and direction of the chemical shift changes for the HPIP ligand

Table 1. Chemical shift changes for the resonances of the Δ - and Λ - $[Ru(bpy)_2(HPIP)]^{2+}$ upon binding to $d(GTCGAC)_2$, at 303 K

Position	Free	Δ		Λ	
		Bound	$\Delta\delta$	Bound	$\Delta\delta$
3,3'	8.62	8.63	0.01	8.66	-0.04
4,4'	8.15	8.18	0.03	8.21	0.05
5,5'	7.63	7.48	-0.03	7.61	-0.02
6,6'	7.92	7.51	-0.03	7.96	0.04
	7.70	7.94	0.02	7.72	0.02
a	8.10	7.70	0.0	7.72	-0.38
b	7.98	7.60	-0.50	7.80	-0.18
c	7.98	7.7	-0.28	7.80	-0.18
i	8.72	8.35	-0.37	8.45	-0.27
j	7.18	6.97	-0.21	7.03	-0.15
k	7.63	7.50	-0.13	7.55	-0.08
l	7.18	6.97	-0.21	7.03	-0.15
	8.12	8.02	-0.10	8.04	-0.08

protons are indicative of selective intercalation of this ligand with $d(GTCGAC)_2$ by both the enantiomers.

As shown in Table 2, addition of Δ - and Λ - $[Ru(bpy)_2(HPIP)]^{2+}$ to $d(GTCGAC)_2$ induced a similar pattern of changes in the chemical shifts of the resonances from the hexanucleotide. The sugar C3H2'-H2'' and G4H2'-H2'' protons showed the largest chemical shift changes, suggesting that both the enantiomers bind in the hexanucleotide major groove. Addition of Δ - or Λ - $[Ru(bpy)_2(HPIP)]^{2+}$ to the hexanucleotide also induced obvious perturbations for the T2H6, C3H6, G4H8 and A5H8 resonances.

Table 2 Chemical shift changes for d(GTCGAC)₂ resonances upon addition of Δ - and Λ -[Ru(bpy)₂HPIP]²⁺, at a metal complex-to-duplex ratio of 1:0, in 10 mM phosphate (pD 7.0) containing 20 mM NaCl at 303 K

	BH6/H8		H1'		H2'		H2''	
	Δ	Λ	Δ	Λ	Δ	Λ	Δ	Λ
G ₁	8.02 (0.02)	7.97 (-0.03)	6.10 (-0.00)	6.05 (-0.05)	2.73 (0.02)	2.74 (0.03)	2.82 (0.01)	2.80 (-0.01)
T ₂	7.45 (-0.08)	7.48 (-0.05)	6.24 (0.02)	6.25 (0.03)	2.29 (0.03)	2.29 (0.03)	2.52 (-0.05)	2.52 (-0.05)
C ₃	7.41 (-0.10)	7.45 (-0.06)	5.74 (0.01)	5.74 (0.02)	2.02 (-0.03)	1.96 (-0.07)	2.32 (-0.11)	2.35 (-0.08)
G ₄	7.90 (-0.04)	7.89 (-0.05)	5.62 (-0.04)	5.61 (-0.05)	2.63 (-0.12)	2.58 (-0.17)	2.60 (-0.15)	2.58 (-0.17)
A ₅	8.28 (+0.07)	8.35 (+0.12)	6.31 (+0.04)	6.33 (+0.02)	2.67 (0.0)	2.68 (0.01)	2.89 (0.01)	2.89 (0.01)
C ₆	7.35 (-0.03)	7.43 (+0.05)	6.10 (+0.01)	6.05 (-0.04)	2.11 (-0.01)	2.19 (0.07)	2.11 (-0.01)	2.19 (0.07)

Two-dimensional NOE spectra of the hexanucleotide with Δ - or Λ -enantiomer were recorded, at mixing time from 150 to 400 ms, to obtain a more detailed picture of the binding. Fig. 1 shows two expansions of 250 ms mixing time NOESY spectra of d(GTCGAC)₂ with added Δ - and Λ -[Ru(bpy)₂(HPIP)]²⁺. Intermolecular NOE cross-peaks between the HPIP (Hj and Hl) and the hexanucleotide major groove protons (C3H6 and G4H8) were observed when the Δ -enantiomer was added. While for the Λ -enantiomer, only intermolecular NOE cross-peak between the Hj and the G4H8 was observed, and its intensity was much weaker than that of the Δ -enantiomer. The NOESY data together with the chemical shift changes of the metal complexes and the hexanucleotide indicate that both the Δ - and Λ -enantiomers bind the d(GTCGAC)₂ in the major groove. However, it appears that the Λ -enantiomer does not intercalate as deeply as the Δ -enantiomer.

Probing DNA binding with circular dichroism spectroscopy :

CD spectra may give the information on how the helicity of the DNA chain influences the electronic transitions of a bound complex. CD spectra of the metal complexes in the presence of CT-DNA are depicted in Fig. 2. In the MLCT band of CD spectra of Δ -1, binding to DNA produced a positive change in the long wavelength region (~470 nm) and a negative change in the short wavelength region (~420 nm). For Λ -1, positive changes in both the long and short wavelength regions were observed. In the exciton region of the CD spectra, around 295 nm, considerable changes were seen when Δ -1 and Λ -1 interacted with CT-DNA. Δ -1 increased the exciton CD when bound to DNA, whereas Λ -1 decreased it. A similar trend was observed for isomers of

Fig. 1. Expansion of the NOESY spectra (250 ms mixing time) of d(GTCGAC)₂ and (A) Δ -[Ru(bpy)₂(HPIP)]²⁺ and (B) Λ -[Ru(bpy)₂(HPIP)]²⁺, at a metal-to-duplex ratio of 1:0 at 303 K. The expansion shows the hexanucleotide base and metal complex aromatic protons

complex 4. Binding of Δ -2 and Λ -2 to CT-DNA induced small changes in both the MLCT and the exciton region of the CD spectra. In the presence of DNA, however, almost identical CD changes of equal magnitude but opposite sign were observed for the enantiomers of complex 3 in both the visible and the UV region.

Changes in the metal complex CD spectra upon binding to polynucleotide may result from either structural or electronic perturbations. Although changes of CD indicate interaction of the complex with DNA, it is not possible to interpret these changes in absolute structure terms. From the results we can see that upon binding to DNA, the CD spectra changes of Δ -1 and Λ -1 are somewhat different, which may suggest different intercalative binding geometries

Fig. 2. CD spectra of Δ -1 and Λ -1, Δ -2 and Λ -2, Δ -3 and Λ -3, Δ -4 and Λ -4 in 5 mmol dm⁻³ tris-HCl and 50 mmol dm⁻³ NaCl (pH 7.2) in the absence (solid curves) and presence of CT-DNA (dashed curves), the visible region is presented on an expanded scale at the right panel, [Ru] = 20 μ mol dm⁻³, [DNA] = 200 μ mol dm⁻³, path length = 1.0 cm. The CD spectra of CT-DNA are subtracted from those of the mixtures

of the isomers. On the other hand, for isomers of complex 3, which also binds through an intercalative binding mode, similar CD changes were seen in the presence of DNA, implying a similar manner in their interaction with the double helix. For the weakly binding complexes Δ -2 and Λ -2, very small spectral perturbations were observed upon adding CT-

DNA in this experiment.

Photophysical studies : Probing DNA binding with visible absorption and fluorescence spectroscopy :

The binding of Δ - and Λ -isomers to CT-DNA led to hypochromism and red-shifts of the metal-to-ligand charge transfer (MLCT) transition and/or the π - π^* intraligand (IL) transitions of the intercalating ligand in the visible region of the ruthenium species. Table 3 summarizes some of the spectra changes when the isomers bind to CT-DNA. In the presence of DNA, the absorption spectra perturbation for isomers of complex 2, esp. Λ -2, are obviously very smaller

Table 3 Electronic absorption spectra changes upon addition of CT-DNA

Complex	Absorption $\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)		Bathochromism	Hypochromism
	Free	Bound	$\Delta\lambda$ (nm)	%
Δ -1	458	464	6	24.5
Λ -1	458	464	6	21.1
Δ -2	456	458	2	15.3
Λ -2	456	458	2	10.6
Δ -3	434	442	8	23.4
Λ -3	350	354	4	20.8
Δ -4	444	444	0	15.8
Λ -4	444	444	0	11.2
	370	376	6	38.0

than that of the remaining complexes. Generally, the Δ -isomers showed somewhat more hypochromism than that of the Λ -isomers. The values of hypochromism of Δ -3 and Λ -3 upon binding to DNA are in fact very small. Δ -1 and Λ -1, Δ -3, Λ -3, Δ -4 and Λ -4 produced a significant hypochromism in both the MLCT and/or the IL bands on addition of DNA. Although the spectral changes in the MLCT bands of isomers of complex 4 are relatively small, but their IL bands perturbations are significant. For each set of the isomers, the spectral changes for their individual enantiomer differ only slightly from each other, indicating that their interactions with DNA are not very different. The results suggest an intimate association of these complexes with DNA and also it is likely that the complexes in this group may bind to the helix by intercalation. However, for Δ -2 and Λ -2, much less spectral changes are seen in the presence of DNA. The spectral characteristics are very similar to⁵ those of [Ru(phen)₃]²⁺, suggesting a relative weak association of this isomers to the helix.

Enantiomers of complexes 1 and 2 can emit luminescence in tris-buffer at ambient temperature, but no luminescence was observed for 3 and 4. Upon addition of CT-DNA,

their luminescence behavior was distinctly different. Solutions of Δ -1 and Λ -1 exhibited an obvious enhancement of emission intensity when DNA was added, but only a small difference between them was observed. Solutions of Δ -2 and Λ -2, however, showed much less luminescence enhancement under similar conditions, although more luminescence enhancement of Δ -2 over Λ -2 was observed. For the isomers of complexes 3 and 4, all of their luminescence can be retrieved by the addition of double-stranded DNA. The emission intensities of Δ -3 or Λ -3 increased steadily in the presence of increasing amount of DNA, and no obvious difference of emission behavior between the two isomers was observed. On the other hand, the luminescence increase found for Λ -4 was about one-third of that of Δ -4. A similar phenomenon has also been found between Δ -[Ru(phen)₂DPPZ]²⁺ and Λ -[Ru(phen)₂DPPZ]²⁺, but this does not mean that there is significant enantioselection between the isomers¹⁴.

The trend of luminescence enhancement between complexes 1 and 2 upon addition of double helical DNA is consistent with the results of the absorption titration. This observation may be explained by the fact that in complex 1, the *ortho*-phenolic group of HPIP would be considered to be almost coplanar with the imidazole ring owing to the formation of an intramolecular hydrogen bond with the nitrogen atom of the imidazole ring^{34,35}, which may result in the close stacking between HPIP and the DNA base pairs. On the other hand, in complex 2, the large naphthyl ring may lie out-of-plane of the imidazole ring, and so partial intercalation of the HNAIP ligand may be expected upon addition of DNA. The greater increase in luminescence observed for Δ -2 in presence of DNA over that for Λ -2 may imply their different association with the helix. In contrast to complex 1, there was no luminescence for the isomers of complex 3 in buffer solution. This may be due to the strong deactivation of the nitro group in complex 3 in solvent water³⁶. Upon binding to double helical DNA, their luminescence were retrieved, which may be the result of intercalating the ligand HNOIP into the DNA base pairs, shielding the ligand, especially the nitro group from solvent water. The similar luminescence retrieval of Δ -3 and Λ -3 upon addition of DNA are again consistent with the results of their absorption titration, indicating their similar mode of association with the double helix.

Enantioselectivity of binding to DNA :

Equilibrium dialysis experiments may offer the opportunity to examine the enantioselectivities of the complexes binding to DNA. Racemic solutions of the complexes studied were dialyzed against CT-DNA with stirring for 48 h,

and which were then subjected to CD analysis. The dialyzate of complex 2 showed two CD signals with a positive peak around 275 nm and a negative peak around 295 nm, but no CD signal appeared for complex 1, nor for 3 or 4. Quite interestingly, during the dialysis process, we observed the CD signals of the dialyzates of complexes 1 and 4, but not of 3. This phenomenon stimulated us to further examine the dialysis process at different intervals of time. Fig. 3 shows the CD signals of the dialyzate of complex 1 with varying dialysis time. From the beginning to 26 h, the CD signals

Fig. 3. CD spectra of the dialyzates of complex 1 after dialysis against CT-DNA for (A) 6, 14, 20, 26 and (B) 26, 32, 38, 44 h with the solution stirred, [Ru] = 50 $\mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ [DNA] = 1.0 mmol dm^{-3}

started from none to the maximum magnitude, and then decreased. By the end, they disappeared. A similar trend was also seen with complex 4. From the beginning to the end, no CD signal appeared for complex 3.

From the equilibrium dialysis experiments, it may be concluded that there is no significant enantioselectivity in the interactions of complex 1, as well as 3 and 4, with double strand B-DNA. During the dialysis experiments, the CD

signals of the dialyzate of complex **1**, as well as **4**, experienced a disappearing – appearing – disappearing pattern, which may be ascribed to the different binding rates of the isomers. From the experiments we can be said that the Λ -enantiomer binds more rapidly than the Δ -enantiomer. The different binding rates observed in our experiments may be as a consequence of diastereomeric orientation effects of the chromophore and of different penetrations upon binding to the double helix. For complex **3**, the absence of any CD signal during the dialysis experiments may suggest a similar manner of interaction of their isomers with the double helix. For complex **2**, the exhibited CD spectra are assigned to be the Δ -form, as judged by comparing the CD spectra of its Δ -enantiomer. Although from the spectroscopy titrations there seems to be a preference for binding of Δ -enantiomer over that of Λ -enantiomer with CT-DNA, the Λ form is preferred in the dialysis experiment. Such behavior is unusual, but it is not without precedence³⁷

Viscosity measurements :

Increasing amounts of the isomers of complexes **1**, **3** and **4** increased the relative viscosity of rod-like CT-DNA, and again there was no obvious difference between each set of the enantiomers. The observed increase in relative viscosity occurs as a result of a length increase of the duplex on intercalation of the complex. On the other hand, neither the Δ -2 nor Λ -2 showed the effect on DNA viscosity expected from the classical intercalation model. The data for the Λ -2 presented in Fig. 4 show that Λ -2 did not appreciably alter DNA viscosity, which is very similar to that of the groove-binding antibiotic (Hoechst 33258), suggesting a nonintercalative and possibly a groove-binding mode. Binding of Δ -2 decreased the relative specific viscosity of DNA, which may be explained by a binding mode that produces bends or kinks in the DNA helix and thus reduces its effective length and, concomitantly, its viscosity.

Conclusion :

These varied experiments on a series of designed chiral complexes of ruthenium(II), when taken together, may provide a detailed picture of binding of these complexes to the double helix. The results suggest that both the Δ - and Λ -[Ru(bpy)₂(HPIP)]²⁺ intercalate into the base pairs of the d(GTCGAC)₂ via HPIP from the major groove, and the Δ -enantiomer intercalates more deeply than the Λ -enantiomer. For the complexes which bind avidly to DNA by intercalation, there is no noticeable enantioselectivity between the Δ - and Λ -enantiomers. Both of their enantiomers can intercalate into DNA base pairs. However, for the weakly bound Δ -2 and Λ -2, their binding modes seem to be different. Λ -2 may bind through a partial intercalative mode, whereas Δ -2

Fig. 4. Effects of increasing amounts of (●) Δ -2 and (■) Λ -2 on the relative viscosity of CT-DNA; temp. = 28.0 ($\pm$ 0.1) $^{\circ}$. [DNA] = 0.5 mmol dm⁻³, r = [Ru]/[DNA].

may bind in the DNA groove. Different binding rates of individual enantiomers of complexes **1** and **4** to DNA are observed through dialysis experiment. The Λ -enantiomer binds more rapidly than the Δ -enantiomer and their different penetration into the DNA base-pairs upon binding to the double helix is responsible.

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